

MARVIC
MRV for carbon farming

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Mid-term Data Management Plan

MARVIC

Deliverable 7.2

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Project consortium

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
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Executive Summary

This document is an update of the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the MARVIC project. The DMP establishes the framework for managing research data, aligning with Grant Agreement (Article 15 Data Protection) and GDPR norms. We aim to align with FAIR data principles and implement Open Science practices, ensuring that all data generated and collected are managed to remain accessible, interoperable, and reusable beyond the project's lifespan. This DMP specifies data types and formats, metadata provisions, and the use of persistent identifiers for data findability. Trusted repositories for secure data storage are identified, alongside protocols for data sharing, addressing legal, ethical, and intellectual property concerns.

As a 'living' document, this mid-term DMP summarises the data management practices and needs for the first 24 months of the MARVIC project and will be finalized by June 2027. Through this DMP, the MARVIC consortium commits to responsible data stewardship, ensuring data longevity and maximizing its potential impact in the scientific community.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CD&E	Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
CF	Carbon Farming
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifiers
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
IP	Intellectual Property
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LUST	Land Use and Soil Type
MRV	Monitoring, Reporting and Verification
MST	Management Support Team
OPC	Operational Processing Chain
PID	Persistent Identifiers
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The MARVIC project is a Horizon Europe Soil Mission project, launched in June 2023 to support the EU [Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Certification \(CRCF\) Regulation](#), a crucial step in scaling up carbon removal activities and boost faith in European carbon farming schemes. The main goal of MARVIC is to develop and test a framework for the design of harmonized, context-specific Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) systems for assessing soil carbon stock changes and GHG emissions in agriculture. These MRV systems should include the core features: (i) alignment with EU CRCF regulation, (ii) balancing costs and accuracy, (iii) accounting for local context, (iv) reducing administrative burden and (v) considering non-permanence risks. With the context-specific approach, we recognize that across Europe there is a large variability of farm types and land management activities, pedo-climatic conditions, data accessibility, existing data infrastructure and user needs, including desired geographical coverage. Therefore, MARVIC works with 26 test cases in 12 partner countries to understand the impact of these different contexts on choices for MRV system.

Effective data management is key to the success of the MARVIC project, which emphasizes open science practices balanced with the protection of commercial and private interests. Our Data Management Plan (DMP) addresses this by providing clear guidelines for every stage of data handling, from creation to long-term storage. It specifies the types of data repositories all MARVIC beneficiaries use and outlines procedures for secure, long-term data preservation.

Task 7.3 is responsible for developing the data management strategy and updating DMP. . In compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679), we provide detailed guidelines for organizing interviews and workshops to ensure that personal data protection is a top priority for all beneficiaries. The DMP guides MARVIC beneficiaries in effectively archiving, storing and sharing data according to FAIR data principles and Open Science practices.

The data manager (EV ILVO, supported by the MARVIC Steering Committee), is responsible for setting up the DMP and for ensuring that all beneficiaries understand and adhere to the FAIR data principles – making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The Data Management Committee (DMC, consisting of representatives from each partner and is led by EV ILVO) oversees that data, including metadata, is consistently managed, easily accessible during the project, and suitably archived for future use by researchers and the public.

This is the updated version of the initial DMP published in December 2023, including data management practices in the first 24 months of MARVIC.

Note that a DMP is a 'living' document, designed to evolve as the project progresses and adapt to significant changes. The DMP will be finalized in May 2027

2. Data Summary

2.1 Purpose

Data are being gathered and re-used in MARVIC for the following main purposes:

- 1. Assessment and Mapping of Mitigation Potential:** This involves analysing and mapping spatial variability of the mitigation potential of CF practices at landscape level across Europe and assessing the impact that human and natural disturbances might have on the mitigation potential (WP4).
- 2. Development of MRV Systems for CF:** We will either identify, improve and/or develop and pre-assemble the building blocks that are required for the development of efficient and cost-effective MRV systems, including smart combinations of data sources and data acquisition techniques (T2.1, T2.2, T2.4, T2.5), smart sampling strategies (T2.3), modelling approaches and guidelines for their implementation/improvement (T3.1, T3.2), digital technologies and tools, such as Operational Processing Chains (OPCs) (T3.3, T3.4).
- 3. Guiding Principles for CF Schemes:** We will define guiding principles and rules for CF schemes, particularly concerning MRV systems under different Land Use and Soil Types (LUSTs) (T1.1, T1.2, T1.4).
- 4. Framework for MRV Systems:** We will develop a robust framework for the design of harmonized, context-specific MRV systems to track payment systems for CF ('MRV Framework'), fit for European public and private CF schemes (T1.5).
- 5. Testing of MRV System Options:** We will test various MRV system options outlined in the MRV Framework across national/regional test cases. This will include testing in different contexts that vary due to differences in soil types, land use types, management practices, data source availability and digital tool readiness and that incorporate land managers' experiences and capabilities (T1.3).

6. **Socio-Economic Feasibility Assessment:** We will assess the socio-economic feasibility of CF practices and schemes, considering the costs of practices, MRV systems, potential revenues, and other benefits associated with soil health (WP5).

7. **Community Engagement and Long-term Strategies:** We seek to engage with the wider stakeholder community to develop long-term strategies for the implementation and continuous improvement of MRV systems by building on new knowledge, new field evidence, new technologies and upcoming data availability and harmonization, building upon an open access approach (WP6).

The MARVIC project's data and generated knowledge serve the needs of diverse target groups. For policymakers, the data and knowledge generated support the development of MRV methodologies in line with the CRCF regulation, the development of TIER 3 monitoring that can be used for LULUCF purposes, and the development of CAP and other policy-related incentives. Scientific communities benefit from these data by advancing research and gaining in-depth knowledge about MRV methodologies — for example, to test and refine process-based models and Operational Processing Chain (OPC) integrating various data layers and models for monitoring carbon budget, to evaluate the climate change impact on the mitigation potential of CF practice and to gain insights into cost (breakdown) and user preferences of MRV systems. Corporate Sustainability Officers and CF Scheme Developers can use these data and knowledge for strategic planning in proactive climate actions, access an EU-approved MRV framework to distinguish genuine sustainability efforts from greenwashing and streamline their certification processes for sustainability.

The main purposes remain relevant and the updates on research data and management data are provided below.

2.2 Research Data

In MARVIC, our focus lies in integrating knowledge, data, methods, and technological/digital solutions. We will re-use data from past and ongoing EU and national projects related to the 'primary' (i.e. data and models) and 'composite' (partly assembled, e.g. assimilation of EO in models) building blocks of MRV systems. Additionally, we will provide guidelines and identify the requirements for data harmonization, interoperability, data infrastructure and sharing, and guidelines for OPC development and assessment of accuracy/uncertainty. Beyond the technical aspects, we will consider socio-economic factors, including user and developer preferences, to enhance the smart assembly of these building blocks leading to the integration of operational processing chains in context-specific MRV Frameworks. Our data involves two primary categories:

i) Generated Data

Primary data are collected from 26 test cases for different purposes. Under T2.2, metadata of 73 benchmark site datasets to evaluate and validate modelling, including key site characteristics, measured variables and management practices, were collected and made openly available to the scientific community. Farm data surveys (T2.5) from 12 partner countries were conducted to inventory and categorise available and relevant farm data types across Europe and to identify the needs and solutions to achieve full interoperability with MRV systems. Biomass data of cover crops has been collected in 2024–2025 to test a remote sensing-based biomass sampling protocol (T2.4); additional data will be collected in 2025–2026. Soil sampling campaigns will be conducted to evaluate the smart sampling tools (T2.3). Cost items of CF practices and MRV systems will be collected in test cases to evaluate cost effectiveness (T5.1).

Improved versions of models and OPCs (operational processing chain assembling data and models) will also be published (T3.2&T3.3). Datasets on the CF mitigation potential of five ecosystems, based on literature analysis, were generated and published (T4.1). Spatial maps will be created and validated in test cases with the aim to provide insight into the mitigation potential of CF practices for specific regions in Europe (T4.3).

ii) Re-used Data

The MARVIC metadata catalogue (T2.1) is a source book of metadata of relevant FAIR data sources for MRV systems including long-term experimental sites, Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) locations, LUCAS, on-farm and national monitoring sites, remote sensing solutions and literature reviews. This catalogue harvests data from accessible databases, maps, data infrastructures and harmonization initiatives (such as those developed by the SoilWise, ClieNFarms and EJP SOIL projects) covering soils, land use and meteorology, that are available at farm, regional, national and EU levels. It also includes or will include data from other tasks within MARVIC, such as metadata of benchmark site (T2.2), farm data (T2.5) and the model catalogue (T3.1).

Models provided by beneficiaries are used, including RothC-based models, SAFYE-CO₂, BASGRA, STICS, LandscapeDNDC, Yasso, CARAT, APSIM, C-tool, PaSim, CNgrass, etc (T3.2). To evaluate the socio-economic factors (WP5), secondary data were collected from Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN), Integrated

Administration and Control System (IACS), national inventories, National or European public statistics, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and other literature.

Generally, documents are saved in PDF, videos in MP4, software, and code in their native languages complemented by explanatory reports. Data will be stored in open, program-independent formats like CSV, TXT, and PNG. Table 1 provides an overview of the types, formats, and sizes of data generated and reused and includes the current status if the corresponding deliverable has been submitted.

Table 1 Type, format, and size of data that is/will be collected and generated in each WP

	Data type	Data format	Data size
WP1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report on analysis of current MRV systems (<i>Published</i>, 10.5281/zenodo.14742205); - Report on rules and guiding principles for the MRV framework (<i>submitted for internal use</i>); - Report on MRV framework; - Report on MRV test cases 	DOC(X), XLS(X), PPT(X), PDF	<10 GB
WP2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MRV metadata catalogue (<i>Published for internal use</i>); - Open-source datasets of benchmark sites (<i>Published</i>, report: 10.5281/zenodo.11912020 and dataset: 10.5281/zenodo.11912019); - Report on benchmark site guidelines; - Report on smart soil sampling decision tool; - Report on remote-sensing-based biomass sampling protocol; - Report on remote sensing solutions for MRV - Metadata for farm data sources 	DOC(X), XLS(X), PDF, YAML, CVS, GMS, GDX, R, SHP. TIF, XML,	<100 GB
WP3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model codes; - Model catalogue; - Code of OPC & prototypes; - Methodological framework for monitoring; - Guidelines for documenting model and OPC performance; 	DOC(X), XLS(X), PDF, TXT, RDS, XML, NETCDF, JSON, SHP. TIF, HTML, PY	~1TB
WP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report on mitigation potential (<i>Published</i>, report: 10.5281/zenodo.15393410 and dataset: 10.5281/zenodo.14408831); 	DOC(X), XLS, GEOTIFF, PDF	<100GB

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report on protocol for climate change modelling (<i>submitted for internal use</i>); - Report on radiative forcing; - Report on the impact of climate change on soil carbon sequestration potential; - Mitigation potential maps; - Report on mitigation potential maps. 		
WP5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report on cost guidelines (<i>Published, 10.5281/zenodo.14230218</i>); - Report on impact of CAP post-2020 on climate change mitigation by C sequestration; - Report on financial mechanisms; - Cost allocation of CF practices/schemes; - Report on Perspectives on MRV design; - Report on Policy coherence assessment. 	DOC(X), XLS(X), DO, DTA, PDF, PPT(X), TXT, CVS, GMS, GDX, R, RDATA, SMCL	<20GB
WP6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (<i>submitted for internal use</i>); - MARVIC website (<i>Published, https://www.project-marvic.eu/</i>); - Report on stakeholder map and engagement (<i>submitted for internal use</i>); - Post-project implementation plan; - Policy brief (<i>Published, Double counts: 10.5281/zenodo.14524206, Baseline: 10.5281/zenodo.14524127, and 10.5281/zenodo.14524218, uncertainty reporting: 10.5281/zenodo.14761277</i>); - Recorded webinars (<i>Published, https://www.project-marvic.eu/resources</i>) - Newsletters (<i>published 3 editions</i>). 	DOCX, PDF, HTML, MP4	<10GB
WP7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact list of the consortium (<i>for internal use</i>); - Data management plan (<i>Published, 10.5281/zenodo.14742109</i>); - Recording of internal webinars and meetings (<i>for internal use</i>) - Meeting minutes (<i>for internal use</i>). 	XLS(X), DOCX, PDF, MP4	<20GB

2.3 Management Data

Management data from MARVIC beneficiaries, for instance, personal contact information, has been systematically collected and utilized throughout the project for essential management

(WP7) and communication activities (WP5 and WP6). Besides the beneficiaries, stakeholders, such as professionals in the agrifood chain, researchers, private companies, policymakers and public authorities, farmers and representatives of farmers and landowners, will participate in interviews, surveys, focus groups, webinars, workshops, and other activities. Below, we describe how data from MARVIC beneficiaries and external stakeholders are handled.

Key categories of management data for MARVIC include:

Project Coordination Data: These data are collected and processed by EV ILVO (WP7) and include contact details and other relevant personal information of MARVIC consortium members. This data is crucial for organizing consortium meetings, workshops, and coordinating project tasks.

Farm Activity Data: Collected farmers' data from test cases will be anonymized to ensure privacy and confidentiality and usage of the farm's geo-information is in strict accordance with any existing agreements as stated in CA.

Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Data: These data are managed by SAE, more particularly the team responsible for WP6 (Communication and Dissemination).and involve gathering contact information of stakeholders to share project information, newsletters, webinars and other communication activities. In addition, three End-user forums leaders—Agrosolutions for the Market Forum, INRAE for the Climate Advocacy Forum and Teagasc for the Policy Forum—are responsible for managing personal data collected during engagement activities for their End-user forums. All beneficiaries are responsible for managing personal data collected in local workshops in accordance with established guidelines (WP5).

Human Resources Data: Pertaining to each beneficiaries, this data includes personnel details necessary for project administration and coordination.

In managing these data, MARVIC adheres to stringent rules concerning data collection, processing, storage, and deletion, ensuring compliance with both primary and secondary data management standards. Critical to this process is the adherence to the EU GDPR 2016/679, particularly when handling personal data. MARVIC's guideline on handling interview/workshop personal data, along with a consent form, was developed to provide step-by-step guidance before and after the activities. Each partner organization responsible for conducting interviews or facilitating workshop discussions is accountable for ensuring the data is secure. These

aspects are further detailed in the ethics section (below), underscoring our commitment to ethical data management practices in the MARVIC project.

3. FAIR Data

Digital research data generated in MARVIC will follow FAIR principles of ‘Findability’, ‘Accessibility’, ‘Interoperability’, and ‘Reusability’.

3.1 Making Data Findable

Each shared dataset or document is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) as its persistent identifier (PID), ensuring stable and long-term identification and accessibility. Also, each version of a dataset or document is assigned a separate DOI, while a version-independent DOI is used to reference all versions collectively. For example, Deliverable 4.1, *Carbon Farming Mitigation Potential: Evaluating the mitigation potential (and uncertainties) of carbon farming practices*, has version 1.0 with DOI ([10.5281/zenodo.14357697](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14357697)), and version 2.0 with DOI ([10.5281/zenodo.15393411](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15393411)), along with a general DOI ([10.5281/zenodo.15393410](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15393410)) that cites all versions. To facilitate findability, the metadata following the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF), ISO19139, INSPIRE metadata, or Dublin Core standards is provided for datasets and documents. This metadata (will) include crucial details like dataset title, authors, creation date, a concise summary, and carefully selected search keywords relevant to the research domain, enhancing discoverability and potential re-use. These keywords are periodically reviewed—for instance, during the refinement of the metadata catalogue (T2.1) and Glossary (WP1)—and updated to accurately reflect the project’s evolving research scope. Furthermore, the metadata will be structured and formatted to allow efficient harvesting and indexing by various data repositories and search platforms (e.g. Zenodo, EJP Soil Data and SoilWise repository), ensuring our data is easily findable.

3.2 Making Data Accessible

Data accessibility is anchored in the strategic use of trusted repositories and robust data management practices. We have chosen to deposit our datasets and documents in a trusted open data repository, Zenodo, and have created [the MARVIC project](#) community on the platform. Guidelines have been provided to ensure that new uploads to Zenodo are properly submitted, associated with datasets or other relevant documents, and assigned to the MARVIC community. So far, documents such as project deliverables, policy briefs, datasets, publications, conference proceedings and webinar presentations have been uploaded to Zenodo. Once deposited, these documents are linked to the Zenodo Community of the EU

Open Research Repository and are also made available through the MARVIC project website (<https://www.project-marvic.eu>), which serves as a central hub for disseminating project outcomes to a broad audience.

Additionally, the improved versions of the models and OPCs, along with model ensembles, will be shared through platforms such as GitLab. Initially, we planned to establish a project-specific GitLab site managed by INRAE, where the latest versions of the models will be consistently updated and maintained. However, due to the distributed ownership of different model codes and capacity constraints, this approach is challenging. As an alternative, we will prepare a summary document detailing the model evaluation process, including the steps taken for model improvement and the model versions used. For models that are already well-developed and documented on external repositories, appropriate references will be included. This summary document will be uploaded to Zenodo for public access ensuring that comprehensive and up-to-date sources are provided. The mitigation potential maps will be published on an existing GIS-host website, for instance, the EUSO data platform.

For internal consortium access, the ILVO SharePoint platform, which is a cloud-based service hosted by Microsoft for businesses of all sizes, is used to facilitate collaborative research efforts. Each WP has a dedicated MS TEAMS channel and folders are created for all tasks, allowing consortium members to access documents related to task activities.

3.3 Making Data Interoperable

MARVIC is aligned with OpenAIRE Guidelines regarding FAIR data management in Horizon Europe for enhancing online interoperability, ensuring that our metadata utilizes open, external vocabularies and is stored internally in a format that enables export to various other formats. We (will) generate and reuse experimental data, images, text files, numerical inputs and outputs of model runs, webinar recordings and other digital tools. Generally, documents are stored in PDF, videos in MP4, software and code in the software language they were written in and are accompanied with explanatory reports. Datasets are stored in open formats (e.g., CSV, TXT, PNG, etc.) or commonly used ones (e.g. XLS(X), DOC(X), TIF, etc.). Regarding data harmonization, interoperability, data infrastructure, and sharing, we are closely working together with other EU projects (e.g. EJP SOIL, ORCaSa, MRV4SOC CREDIBLE, and SoilWise) and the EUSO knowledge repository (JRC) to facilitate the establishment of common standards and harmonization criteria for carbon farming. For example, the MARVIC Metadata Catalogue harvests relevant soil and crop datasets from the EJP SOIL Data Catalogue System, and MARVIC project outputs also contribute to the SoilWise repository to support wider interoperability and data reuse.

3.4 Increase Data Re-usable

To facilitate data validation and re-use, we provided detailed documentation for each dataset. This includes README files covering methodology, codebooks, data cleaning processes, analyses, variable definitions, and units of measurement. For example, README documents or sheets were provided for T2.2 Benchmark site survey, T2.5 Farm data survey and T3.2 model survey. Such thorough documentation helps ensure that data can be correctly interpreted and reanalysed by others. Additionally, we will develop an Intellectual Property (IP) strategy to identify potentially protectable results and manage know-how in accordance with the legal provisions of the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement (CA), where specific rules are outlined to protect project results, addressing issues related to ownership, confidentiality, and protection of know-how developed within the project. Although an IP strategy has not yet been established, we are actively consulting legal experts to ensure it is developed in due course and is aligned with the exploitation strategy.

In line with MARVIC's 'open character,' most results were or will be publicly available after the project's conclusion, facilitating re-use for research purposes. So far, Creative Commons Licenses are used to regulate third-party access to public datasets. We define any restrictions, including embargo periods, balancing open access with the protection of IP rights and researchers' interests. For example, the dataset for Deliverable 4.1. *Carbon Farming Mitigation Potential: Evaluating the mitigation potential (and uncertainties) of carbon farming practices*, has been placed under embargo until December 2027 to ensure sufficient time for publications based on this dataset. Open-access metadata will use Creative Commons Zero (i.e. CC 0), while, publicly available datasets, and mitigation potential maps will be available for scientific purposes free of charge, with Creative Commons Attribution, Non-Commercial and/or ShareAlike (i.e. CC-By, CC-By-NC, or CC-By-SA). The performance of improved models and OPC prototypes will be published in a report, along with output data under a CC-By license. However, access to the codes of models and OPC prototypes must align with institutional policies. For example, the AgriCarbonEO code is free of charge upon request for scientific and educational purposes, but commercial use requires a paid license from Toulouse Tech Transfer. So far, 13 publications, 2 datasets and 2 presentations are available on Zenodo, most of them as open access with CC-By licenses.

4. Allocation of Resources

In MARVIC, we prioritize efficient and cost-effective data management while adhering to the FAIR data principles and plan to minimize storage and archiving costs by leveraging free services and tools, such as Zenodo for open data repository services, and institutional

platforms for secured data storage. Other potential costs include open-access publication fees. SAE, with support of EV ILVO, is responsible for compliance with the EU guidelines on open science requirements, and research under Horizon Europe (WP6). We monitor that Gold Open Access, which provides a copy of the document on the publisher's own website which is open access, is given priority and Green Open Access, which provides access to the document via an online valid repository, is considered as the second option. A guideline document was provided to the consortium defining Gold/Green Open Access, explaining how to deposit articles with open access, and outlining authorship criteria. Each beneficiary manages its own funding for these activities in accordance with the Grant Agreement, ensuring compliance with the project's financial and administrative provisions. All publications are deposited in Zenodo, and also the MARVIC website.

Data management responsibility in MARVIC lies with each beneficiary, ensuring that all data collected, processed, or received from external sources is managed with the necessary authorizations for sharing and use. The project data manager, Hui Xu supported by ILVO's Data Manager Elien Dewitte, and the Data Management Committee (DMC, composed of representatives from each partner and led by the project coordinator), oversees the DMP and regularly updates the DMP (at least yearly). The DMC provides strategic guidance to ensure adherence to the DMP, fostering a collaborative approach to data management across the consortium. The consortium agreed on the handling of research data during and after the end of MARVIC (at least five years preservation after the project end). The strategy will be balanced against the need for confidentiality and compliance with legal requirements.

5. Data Security

In the project lifetime of MARVIC, data not publicly available is securely stored on a collaborative platform, a project-dedicated site MARVIC TEAMS established on ILVO SharePoint, accessible only to consortium members or on institutional servers of partner organizations with restricted access to respective project teams. Furthermore, dedicated folders for research datasets in each WP have been set up, allowing for stricter access control than the main project site, when needed. The MARVIC TEAMS has the following security settings:

1. Consortium members have to receive individual access rights provided by ILVO's SharePoint management system and approved by the MARVIC Management Support Team (MST). This access will be protected with the external account login and the password for each individual user.

2. Risk management, security monitoring, and any other file-/data-related risks will be supported by ILVO ICT team.

Each MARVIC beneficiary bears responsibility for the data they collect, process, and any further processing of previously collected data (secondary use) received from external entities. We also ensure, whether directly from these secondary data providers or indirectly via other consortium members, that necessary authorizations are in place to share and utilize the data within MARVIC, aligning with the research objectives. Data controllers and processors of MARVIC will implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to safeguard the data from unlawful processing. When using secondary data from another MARVIC beneficiary, it must be ensured that this is done in alignment with the restrictions on implementation and exploitation outlined in Attachment I (Background Information) of the CA. This background information can be modified and updated by mutual agreement among the beneficiaries during project lifetime, and it should only be used for purposes for which access rights for implementation and exploitation have been granted.

Research data, in agreement with the consortium, will be stored for five years after the project. The specific arrangements will be decided in the monthly Steering Committee meetings. The data will be archived by the beneficiaries in accordance with their institutional policies. For example, research data generated by EV ILVO will be stored in the ILVO Plant archive. The project website (<https://www.project-marvic.eu>) managed by SEA serves as the contact for public dissemination. It hosts project public deliverables, publications, and other materials such as webinar announcements, news articles, images, videos, links to partner organizations, and knowledge products. Scientific publications will be accessible and discoverable in the mode of Gold or Green open access publishing in the open repositories as stated in the Grant Agreement. Large, re-useable datasets are being—and will continue to be—deposited in an open data repository, i.e. Zenodo and SoilWise repository, selected by the task and sub-tasks leaders during the delivery of the relevant WP results.

6. Ethics

The sharing of data collected and generated by MARVIC is not expected to raise significant ethical concerns as discussed in the Description of the Action (DoA). Most of the ethical considerations were addressed in the ethics-related WPs (WP5, WP6 and WP7), more specifically, the personal information of project partners and stakeholders. The consortium confirms to apply the ethical guidelines of the Horizon Europe project and all relevant EU/national legislation, international conventions, and declarations. This includes the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, the European Convention for the Protection of Human

Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, and GDPR. Any request for erasure of data will be promptly honored, adhering to the 'right to be forgotten.'

The cornerstone of our ethical practice is the informed consent procedure. A GDPR-compliant consent form (see attachment of D6.4 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan – Update 1), prepared by SAE, is provided to participants for online events. In addition, a guideline on how to handle interviews, workshop discussions, and personal data was distributed, along with templates for the Participant Information Form and Informed Consent Form, primarily for activities in WP6 and WP7. The guideline includes information on procedures both before and after the event. Before interviews or workshops, beneficiaries must prepare a participant information form ensuring that all participants clearly understand the purpose of the research and participate voluntarily. Signed consent forms will be stored by the beneficiary that conducted the interview or workshop and will not be shared with the task leader or coordinator team, in order to avoid the exchange of personal data. After the activity, audio or video recordings, if applicable, must be deleted within the agreed timeframe. Personal data will be securely stored, and appropriate anonymisation and pseudonymisation procedures will be applied. Any publications or dissemination of project data will respect the participants' right to privacy. No personal data will be included in published materials without explicit, informed consent from the individuals involved.

For tasks requiring ethical approval, the task lead could submit a request to the ILVO Committee for Ethics in Social Sciences and Humanities (ComESSH) at least 8–12 weeks before data collection begins or alternatively seek approval from another relevant institutional ethics board. For example, the ethical aspects of the online survey on policy coherence (T5.4) have been reviewed and evaluated by the German Association for Experimental Economic Research.

When beneficiaries cooperate with external entities like research institutes, universities, governments, or companies, etc., a detailed data-sharing agreement template, provided by EV ILVO, will be used. This agreement outlines the procedures for data collection, processing, implementation and responsibility, ensuring clarity on how data subjects can raise concerns or complaints.

The Data Management Committee (DMC led by the project coordinator), along with appointed Data Protection Officers (DPOs) at each beneficiary, will oversee the ethical management of data. An initial training on ethical procedures and data protection measures was conducted in January 2024, and the topic of data management have since been regularly addressed as

standing item in the monthly Steering Committee meetings to ensure ongoing awareness of the latest ethical procedures and data protection measures.

7. Acknowledgements

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